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Chemical Examination of

Lindenbergia indica

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LINDENBERGIA *indica* (N. O. Scrophulariaceae) is an annual erect herb found throughout India. The juice of the plant is given in chronic bronchitis and mixed with that of coriander applied to skin eruptions^{1,2}. No work has been reported in literature on this plant. A systematic chemical examination of *L. indica* was, therefore, undertaken and the results are reported in the present communication.

The air-dried powdered plant (2 kg) was extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) in a Soxhlet extractor. The extract was concentrated to a small volume (200 ml) and kept in a refrigerator overnight whereby a yellow mass deposited. The deposit was filtered, washed with petroleum ether, taken in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether (40-60°) removed the waxy material. Further elution with petroleum ether : benzene mixture (7 : 3 v/v) gave a crystalline solid (800 mg) which when recrystallised from benzene afforded needles, m.p. 281°, C₃₀H₅₀O. It was characterised as friedelan-3-β-ol by spectral data^{3,4} and by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 291° and benzoate, m.p. 198-9°.

The defatted plant material was then extracted exhaustively with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the thick viscous mass so obtained was extracted with petroleum ether to remove any waxy material and chlorophyll. The residual mass was extracted with benzene and acetone successively. Benzene extract was concentrated and chromatographed over alumina. Elution with benzene and chloroform (7 : 3 v/v) mixture yielded a compound (670 mg)

which when recrystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture afforded needles, m.p. 310°, C₃₀H₄₈O₃ (M⁺, m/e 456) and characterised as oleanolic acid by comparison of its spectral data^{3,4} and properties of its acetate methyl ester derivative and oxidised product⁵.

The acetone extract was concentrated, dried and extracted with absolute ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated to a syrup. Addition of excess of chloroform to the ethanolic syrup, precipitated a resinous mass. The resinous mass was separated by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated, dissolved in water and kept in a refrigerator for a week, whereby free flavone settled down at the bottom. It was separated and dissolved in a little of dried acetone, adsorbed over magnesol column and eluted with ethyl acetate saturated with water whereby a yellow compound was obtained. The compound on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 24° and identified as 7-hydroxy flavone by analysis, colour reactions, spectral data^{6,7} and preparation of its derivatives. The filtrate obtained after separation of free flavone was extracted with ethylacetate for several times. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over magnesol using ethyl acetate saturated with water as eluate, whereupon a yellow compound was obtained. The compound on crystallisation from methanol : ethanyl acetate mixture (1 : 1 v/v), melted at 185-7° and characterised as quercitrin by m.m.p. and superimposable IR spectrum with authentic sample.

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